

DEVELOPMENT OF ICT COMPETENCE OF PRIMARY SCHOOL TEACHERS IN THE PROCESS OF CONTINUING EDUCATION

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Abstract. *In accordance with the modern needs of primary education, the concept of ICT competence of primary school teachers has been clarified, which refers to the teacher's ability to perform professional activities with the help of information and communication technologies and the formation of ICT literacy of students, readiness to quickly master and introduce new technologies into school practice in accordance with trends in the development of the information society.*

Keywords: *information technologies, Methods of teaching computer literacy, information and communication technologies, formation, training, education.*

The creation of a system of continuing education for the period up to 2020 will be the main innovative task.

Numerous studies have been devoted to the problem of continuing education. This is one of the directions of the educational policy of developed and developing countries. The idea of continuing education was highlighted as the main thesis of the educational policy of the XXI century at the thirtieth session of the UNESCO General Conference in 1999.

The main goal of developing the competence of teachers in the field of information and communication technologies is to prepare them for methodically competent use of ICT in the educational process.

It includes: stimulating the cognitive activity of students and creating motivation for the educational process with the help of ICT; the use of means of informatization of education, depending on the purpose and objectives of the educational process; to conduct general education subjects with the help of ICT, taking into account the learning goals, interests and inclinations of students; possession of methods and techniques of teaching with the help of ICT; monitoring and self-monitoring of educational activities with the help of ICT; self-analysis, self-assessment, including diagnostics based on ICT [1].

The process of continuous development of ICT competence is gradual. The pre-professional stage includes professional orientation to the profession of a teacher. The professional stage is implemented at the levels of secondary vocational and higher vocational education. It assumes purposeful training of students of pedagogical educational institutions in the field of ICT application, including theoretical and practical training, pedagogical practice, course and diploma design, which is the basis for further development of the teacher in the aspect under study.

The post-professional stage is: professional adaptation in an educational institution, the development of professionalism during the period of work in an educational institution, postgraduate studies and advanced training qualifications. All these three stages relate to the institutionalized form of continuing education, as lifelong learning.

There is also a non-institutionalized form of continuing education, which can include self-education.

Self-education is no less important process than education received within the framework of an educational institution. Methodical work on continuous professional development in the form of self-education it is one of the most effective and necessary forms of mastering by a teacher the practice of applying the requirements of new educational standards [11].

Self-education can be presented in two forms: individual and group. In an individual form, the initiator is the teacher himself. The group form is carried out in the form of the work of a methodological association, seminars, workshops, advanced training courses qualifications and others that provide feedback between the results of individual self-education of the teacher [9].

The most important role is played by educational development institutes, which organize training and retraining courses for teaching staff (up to 3 months), open lessons with access to an educational institution, seminars, methodological associations, teacher meetings, pedagogical readings. The study of psychological and pedagogical problems and scientific and methodological training in advanced training courses are embedded in standardized course training programs [2-4].

Based on the above, the idea was formulated development of ICT competence of a student and a primary school teacher who are in a continuous process of developing information and communication competencies based on remote forms of interaction, because this is how optimal conditions can be created for effective support of professional development student and teacher.

It is very important that the ICT competence of a teacher becomes in demand by all participants in the educational process (students, parents, teachers). Unfortunately, neither pedagogical universities nor the CPC pay due attention to teacher training because it requires the development of new methods and forms of work with teachers, the search for which is still ongoing. Therefore, the development of a model of such teacher training is relevant.

Within the framework of educational university courses of special information training, students are expected to master professional activities with the involvement of a teacher-mentor of the school, the result of which are:

- 1) samples of documents issued in a text editor, such as such as: reports on educational, educational and social work, characteristics for a primary school student and the class as a whole, student portfolios, etc.;
- 2) examples of class, group databases; samples of constructed reports, development of lesson schedules;
- 3) the project, archive and address on the Internet of the educational website intended for the organization of educational activities of the class;
- 4) interactive electronic dictionary of terms on the selected subject and implemented in a special shell for creating electronic textbooks;
- 5) an electronic simulator designed to consolidate educational material based on presentation technology;
- 6) an interactive test created in a test shell designed to test and evaluate students' knowledge.

All tasks orient the student to use the possibilities of modern information and communication technologies in his future professional activity. However, without direct

supervision (participation) in the educational process of the school, students experience substantive and methodological difficulties in their implementation.

With the development of remote means, the interaction of participants in the educational process has become more accessible. Students had the opportunity to communicate with teachers, students and their parents using social networks [10].

They have the opportunity to conduct webinars and teleconferences to organize parent meetings.

Thus, with the help of systematic inclusion of bachelors in the educational process schools with continuous interaction with participants of the educational

process using distance forms, the student goes through several stages of professional formation of a teacher [8]:

1) the beginning of studies at the university before passing the training practice through practical and laboratory work on the basis of the educational institution;

2) involvement of future teachers in professional activities during the training practice;

3) writing and defending a final qualifying work with conducting an experiment on the basis of an educational institution;

4) professional adaptation during industrial (pedagogical) practice.

During their studies at a higher educational institution, students of the applied form of the bachelor's degree master the skills to communicate with children and enter with contact them, conduct lessons, a variety of educational activities, conduct systematic individual work, conduct micro-studies, maintain educational documentation, as well as many other skills that cannot be mastered only in the student audience.

The necessary theoretical and practical basis for the use of ICT in the educational process of the school, students of pedagogical colleges are provided with continuous pedagogical practice on the basis of schools. The development of the ICT competence of the teacher at the university stage provides the necessary for every teacher the minimum level of mastering the methods of information activity and information interaction with the help of ICT.

Experience is the main component of personality formed in the learning process. It is possible to obtain it within the framework of informatization of education in the implementation of continuous practical work at school in the context of the integrated use of ICT in the educational process. When organizing work in primary school, the most common use of ICT technologies is to accompany the lesson with a PowerPoint presentation. This became relevant with the advent of the simplest projectors that projected an image on a wall or canvas.

However, information technology does not stand still now interactive whiteboards are actively used. This board is equipped with various devices: markers, pens, remotes. Each interactive whiteboard is designed on the basis of individual software that the teacher should be able to work with.

The skills of working with an interactive whiteboard by a primary school teacher are especially in demand. With the help of flipcharts created in the interactive whiteboard program, physical training sessions, updating of knowledge, control, self-examination of students can be organized, presented projects.

The requirements of the state educational standard of primary general education in the section.

"Requirements for the result of mastering the basic educational program of primary general education" indicate the requirements for students. As a result of the analysis of these requirements, the skills in the field of ICT technologies that a primary school graduate should possess are highlighted:

- actively use ICT tools to solve communicative and cognitive tasks;
- apply various methods of searching, collecting, processing, analyzing, transmitting and interpreting information in accordance with the technologies of the subject, including the ability to enter text using the keyboard, digitally record measured values and analyze images, sounds, etc.;
- prepare your speech and accompany it with audio, video and graphic information;
- comply with the norms of information selectivity, ethics and etiquette;
- work in the school's IOS. [6].

Our research is based on the following theoretical positions:

1. "Competence" in the federal state educational standard of higher education is understood as a set of knowledge, skills and methods of action formed at the university that allow students to ensure their future professional activities.

2. The key competencies, according to A.V. Khutorsky, are the following seven competencies:

1) value-semantic; 2) general cultural; 3) educational and cognitive; 4) informational; 5) communicative; 6) social and labor; 7) competence of personal improvement. 3. Competence is a comprehensive education that includes professional and personal qualities of an employee, allowing him to engage in professional activity, the ability to use his own specialty as a means to implement the educational process (N.V. Kuzmina).

4. Taking into account the diversity of the types of pedagogical activity carried out, a large number of interrelated competencies can be distinguished as part of the professional competence of a teacher, for example, educational, organizational, methodological, scientific, ICT competence, self-education competence, etc.

5. By the ICT competence of a primary school teacher, we understand his ability to carry out professional activities with the help of information and communication technologies and the formation of ICT literacy of students, readiness to quickly master and introduce new technologies into school practice in accordance with the trends in the development of the information society (copyright).

6. Special opportunities and advantages for the formation of ICT competence of teachers are provided by applied forms of bachelor's degree training in pedagogical direction.

Dual training is integrated into the applied bachelor's degree programs, in which the theoretical part of the training takes place on the basis of an educational organization, and the practical part — at the future workplace of a primary school teacher.

The methodology of forming the initial ideas of younger schoolchildren about the functioning and rules of using the subject IOS to perform educational, design and design tasks in the course "Technology". Goals, objectives and content of the module "Computer practice" in the school technology course[7].Methodology of organization of mastering by younger schoolchildren of the educational module "Computer work practice" Fundamentals of hardware and information

security when working with projection and computer equipment. Organization of the search for the required information on the computer, in the local network of the school and in the network.

Internet for solving educational tasks for primary school students. Methods of teaching younger schoolchildren accessible techniques for working with ready-made digital resources:

information retrieval techniques, reading information, algorithms for organizing tasks, reporting. Basics of working in text editors. Methods of teaching primary school students to design and implement texts and illustrations in a text editor. The technique of creating the simplest presentation. Basics of using presentation technology to accompany speeches.

ICT literacy of a younger student as a meta –subject result. Symbolic and symbolic means of presenting information and their use to create models of the studied objects and processes. Methods of teaching younger schoolchildren to build schemes for solving educational and practical problems. The concept of the simplest computer models. The use of ICT tools to activate the solution of communicative and cognitive tasks in the educational process of primary school.

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